

Supporting Information

Structure-function relation of cytokinins determines their differential efficiency in mediating tobacco resistance against *Pseudomonas syringae*

Dominik K. Grobkinsky, Eva-Maria Molin, Federico Bosetto, Kerstin Edelsbrunner, Michal Oravec, Kristýna Večerová, Jan Tríska, Thomas Roitsch

FIGURE S1. Molecular structures of used compounds. Structures were generated with MolView (<https://molview.org/>).

A Amino acid biosynthesis (GO:0008652)

B Amino acid catabolism (GO:0009063)

C Amino acid transport (GO:0008643)

D Primary metabolic process (GO:0044238)

E Carbohydrate metabolic process (GO:0005975)

F Carbohydrate transport (GO:0006865)

FIGURE 4. Global gene expression patterns of the different CK treatments compared to mock for selected GO terms related to amino acid and carbohydrate metabolism and transport at 6 and 24h. Plots show log₂ fold change values of DEGs belonging to the GO terms amino acid biosynthesis (A), amino acid catabolism (B), amino acid transport (C), primary metabolic processes (D), carbohydrate metabolic processes (E), and carbohydrate transport (F) with regard to the different CK treatments compared to the mock control at 6 and 24h. Positive log₂ fold change values (representative for an upregulation of genes) are visualised in grey, negative values (representative for a downregulation of genes) in black.

TABLE S1. Compounds quantified by LC-MS.

Amino acids	Acids	Phenolics	Saccharide groups
Alanine	Citric acid	3-coumaric acid	Disaccharides
Arginine	L-(-)-Malic acid	3-hydroxybenzoic acid	Hexoses
Asparagine	Lactic acid	Caffeic acid	Pentoses
Aspartic acid	Oxalacetic acid	Chlorogenic acid	
Cysteine	Pyruvic acid	Ferulic acid	
Glutamic acid	Shikimic acid	Kaempferol	
Glutamine	Succinic acid	Protocatechuic acid	
Glycine	α -ketoglutaric acid	Quercetin	
Histidine		Vanillic acid	
Hydroxyproline			
Isoleucine			
Leucine			
Lysine			
Methionine			
Phenylalanine			
Proline			
Serine			
Threonine			
Tryptophan			
Tyrosine			
Valine			

TABLE S2. Compounds quantified by GC-MS.

Tocopherol & sterols	Sugars
Campesterol	Fructose
Ergosterol	Glucose
Fucosterol	Sucrose
Stigmasterol	Myo-inositol
α -tocopherol	
β -sitosterol	

TABLE S3. Correlation coefficients for metabolite accumulation at 24h of different CK treatments and *Pst* symptom development and proliferation. Coefficients values of 0.7 and higher (in bold) are considered indicative of a strong correlation.

	<i>Pst</i> symptoms		<i>Pst</i> proliferation		
	6dpi	12dpi	24hpi	48hpi	72hpi
Alanine	0.73	0.30	-0.13	0.45	-0.06
Arginine	0.75	0.51	0.15	0.08	0.08
Asparagine	0.59	0.29	0.19	0.22	-0.02
Aspartic acid	0.41	0.19	-0.13	0.12	-0.03
Glutamic acid	0.43	0.31	0.08	0.06	0.16
Glutamine	0.64	0.45	-0.12	0.31	0.08
Histidine	0.50	0.23	-0.16	0.24	-0.03
Hydroxyproline	-0.71	-0.26	0.23	-0.93	0.03
Isoleucine	0.70	0.41	-0.08	0.13	-0.04
Leucine	0.65	0.44	0.02	0.08	0.06
Methionine	0.38	-0.31	-0.64	0.19	-0.78
Phenylalanine	0.90	0.55	0.04	0.38	-0.01
Proline	0.49	0.09	0.12	0.07	-0.14
Serine	0.63	0.58	0.19	0.10	0.30
Threonin	0.57	0.16	-0.35	0.39	-0.20
Tryptophan	0.55	0.53	-0.16	0.23	0.13
Tyrosine	0.67	0.46	-0.09	0.29	0.09
Valine	0.66	0.42	-0.02	0.24	0.08
Citric acid	-0.79	-0.89	-0.26	-0.41	-0.47
L-(-)-Malic acid	0.80	0.70	0.00	0.42	0.25
Lactic acid	0.66	0.60	0.20	0.22	0.34
Oxalacetic acid	-0.32	-0.38	0.26	-0.02	-0.01
Pyruvic acid	0.06	0.17	0.59	0.20	0.47
Shikimic acid	-0.73	-0.88	-0.26	-0.37	-0.48
Succinic acid	0.10	-0.24	-0.57	0.60	-0.46
α -ketoglutaric acid	-0.10	-0.15	-0.10	0.14	-0.20
3-coumaric acid	0.10	-0.03	0.02	-0.25	-0.26
3-hydroxybenzoic acid	0.17	0.53	0.12	-0.37	0.31
Caffeic acid	0.89	0.53	0.04	0.72	0.15
Chlorogenic acid	-0.79	-0.83	-0.13	-0.49	-0.37
Ferulic acid	-0.18	-0.05	-0.21	-0.62	-0.30
Kaempferol	0.16	0.88	0.70	-0.38	0.83
Protocatechuic acid	0.86	0.18	-0.56	0.60	-0.51
Quercetin	-0.02	0.68	0.61	-0.14	0.81
Vanillic acid	0.71	0.07	-0.12	0.64	-0.21
Disaccharides	0.60	0.43	0.00	0.01	0.04
Hexoses	0.67	0.43	-0.11	0.19	0.00
Pentoses	0.00	0.05	-0.02	-0.18	-0.23
Fructose	0.61	0.28	-0.13	0.23	-0.06
Glucose	0.58	0.31	-0.08	0.15	-0.02
Sucrose	0.62	0.47	0.26	-0.05	0.08
Myo-inositol	0.49	0.28	-0.07	-0.02	-0.23
Campesterol	-0.09	0.72	0.82	-0.43	0.96
Ergosterol	0.19	0.46	-0.04	0.24	0.23
Fucosterol	-0.28	-0.08	0.30	-0.65	-0.01
Stigmasterol	0.14	0.76	0.84	-0.59	0.80
α -tocopherol	0.13	0.60	0.54	-0.08	0.76
β -sitosterol	0.48	0.45	0.04	-0.01	0.17

Note: For correlations, ratios of treatment vs. controls were used for each parameter (symptoms, proliferation, time-point, and compound), i.e., positive coefficients are indicative for weak symptoms/proliferation correlate

with low compound levels and vice versa, while negative coefficients are indicative for weak symptoms/proliferation correlate with high compound levels and vice versa. Hence, negative coefficients indicate positive impact on symptom suppression and restricting pathogen proliferation.